

Readiness for Transition to Natural Farming in New Lucena, Iloilo, Philippines: A Participatory Mixed-Methods Situational Analysis

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Abstract: This study assessed the readiness of New Lucena, Iloilo, Philippines for transition to natural farming and generated evidence for the development of a gender-responsive, community-based extension framework. Using a participatory mixed-methods design, the study drew on household surveys, focus group discussions, key informant interviews, participatory workshops, and a review of local policy documents. Findings showed that participating farmers and stakeholders generally viewed natural farming as a healthier and potentially less costly alternative to conventional farming. Respondents associated natural farming with improved household health, reduced production costs, and opportunities for community learning through demonstration farms and farmer-to-farmer knowledge sharing. However, wider adoption remained constrained by limited technical knowledge and confidence, inadequate access to inputs, weak follow-up extension support, limited youth participation, and uneven institutional coordination. Women played notable roles in composting and home gardening, while youth engagement in farming remained weak. The review indicated that policy support for sustainable and natural farming was present, although implementation was uneven. Overall, the findings suggest that New Lucena has emerging social, organizational, and policy conditions that may support transition to natural farming, but these remain incomplete. The study provides a local evidence base for strengthening a gender-responsive, community-based, and better-coordinated extension framework and illustrates how participatory mixed-methods situational analysis can support SUC extension planning in local agricultural transition contexts. Given the limited survey return, the findings should be interpreted as descriptive of participating respondents and stakeholders rather than statistically generalizable to the entire municipality.

Keywords: natural farming; sustainable agriculture; participatory mixed-methods; agricultural extension; local governance; gender inclusion; youth participation

Introduction

Agriculture remains central to rural livelihoods and local development in many Philippine municipalities, yet farming communities continue to face rising production costs, soil degradation, pest pressures, climate-related risks, and unstable markets. The Philippine Development Plan 2023–2028 identifies the need to build a more sustainable, inclusive, and resilient agriculture and fisheries sector, while national planning for research, extension, and technology transfer also highlights the role of state universities and colleges in supporting locally responsive development interventions [1,2].

Within this broader context, natural farming has gained attention as an approach that reduces dependence on synthetic external inputs and relies more on locally available and biologically based materials such as compost, fermented plant extracts, and indigenous microorganisms. In the Philippines, current organic agriculture priorities continue to emphasize research and development, extension support, capacity building, and stronger local implementation mechanisms [3,4]. Across Southeast Asia, recent regional policy directions similarly promote sustainable agricultural practices, resource efficiency, climate resilience, farmer livelihoods, and knowledge sharing as part of agricultural transformation [5,6]. These concerns are also consistent with broader sustainable development priorities, particularly those related to food security and sustainable agriculture, responsible production, climate resilience, gender inclusion, and multi-stakeholder partnerships.

In New Lucena, Iloilo, interest in natural farming has already emerged through local farmer-led initiatives and community-based advocacy. Some local adopters have begun promoting related practices within their barangays, and the Organic Farmers and Producers Association of New Lucena (OFPANELU) has served as a local platform for participation, knowledge sharing, and mutual support. However, these efforts have remained limited in scale and have not yet resulted in wider municipal adoption. The study's evidence shows that while participating farmers and stakeholders generally viewed natural farming as healthier and potentially less costly than conventional farming, broader transition remained constrained by limited technical confidence, inadequate access to inputs, weak follow-up extension support, uneven institutional coordination, and low youth participation.

These local conditions are consistent with the broader policy direction that sustainable agricultural transition depends not only on farmer interest, but also on effective extension systems, institutional support, and locally grounded implementation. In the Philippine setting, current priorities in organic agriculture and youth-oriented agricultural capacity building indicate that transition to more sustainable farming systems requires more than one-time advocacy and depends on continued training, engagement, and support mechanisms [4,7].

Despite local interest and policy attention, there remains limited municipality-level evidence on how ready farming communities are for transition to natural farming, particularly in relation to farmer aspirations, current knowledge and practices, gender and youth participation, organizational support, and the local policy environment. In New Lucena, this evidence gap is especially important because local motivation already exists, yet practical and institutional constraints continue to shape the pace and direction of adoption. This study therefore assessed the readiness of New Lucena, Iloilo, Philippines for transition to natural farming through a participatory mixed-methods situational analysis. Specifically, it examined farmers' aspirations,

knowledge, attitudes, skills, and practices; identified enabling and hindering factors affecting adoption; mapped relevant organizational and partnership support; and reviewed the local policy context to generate evidence for a gender-responsive, community-based extension framework.

Beyond its local empirical focus, this study may also be positioned as an innovation in SUC extension-oriented situational analysis. Rather than treating situational analysis as a purely descriptive baseline exercise, the study uses a participatory mixed-methods design that integrates household survey data, focus group discussions, key informant interviews, participatory workshops, and policy review to generate evidence directly usable for extension planning. In doing so, it links farmer aspirations and practices with institutional, organizational, gender, youth, and policy conditions that shape the feasibility of natural farming transition in a specific local context. This integrated and extension-directed use of situational analysis provides a practical model for state universities and colleges seeking to design gender-responsive, community-based, and policy-aware extension interventions grounded in local evidence.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a participatory mixed-methods design to assess the readiness of New Lucena, Iloilo, Philippines for transition to natural farming and to examine the local capacities and institutional conditions that may enable or constrain such transition. The design combined quantitative and qualitative forms of inquiry in order to capture both observable patterns and context-specific accounts relevant to natural farming adoption. The quantitative component consisted of a household survey, while the qualitative component consisted of focus group discussions, key informant interviews, participatory workshops, and a review of selected local policies and related documents. Taken together, these methods were used to examine farmers' aspirations, prevailing practices, institutional gaps, and enabling conditions in the municipality. The participatory character of the design was reflected in the use of group-based and stakeholder-engaged methods, including visioning, problem tree analysis, gap analysis, and SWOT analysis, as well as coordination with the Office of the Municipal Agriculturist during data gathering. The design was intended to generate evidence that could inform a gender-responsive, inclusive, and community-based extension framework for New Lucena. The study was designed as a situational analysis for extension planning and did not include experimental trials, yield comparison, soil testing, or cross-municipal comparison. Table 1 summarizes the study's data sources and analytical purpose, while Figure 1 presents the overall workflow of the participatory mixed-methods situational analysis.

Study Site and Participants

The study was conducted in New Lucena, Iloilo, Philippines, which served as the focal site for examining local conditions influencing transition to natural farming. The municipality was retained as the named unit of analysis because its identification was necessary to preserve the contextual, institutional, and policy relevance of the inquiry. Participants were drawn from agricultural communities in different barangays of New Lucena and included selected farmers who were members and non-members of OFPANELU, as well as practitioners of both natural

and conventional farming. The study also included participants representing relevant local and institutional perspectives, including local government personnel, gender and development focal persons, farmer technicians, youth representatives, and other key informants involved in agriculture, municipal planning, and community-based development. In reporting the findings, these groups were described using generalized categories to protect individual confidentiality.

Data Collection

Household Survey. The quantitative component consisted of a household survey conducted in coordination with the Office of the Municipal Agriculturist. The instrument was used to gather information on respondent demographics, farm profiles, knowledge, attitudes, skills, and practices related to natural farming, household roles, perceived barriers, and requested support. A total of 200 household questionnaires were distributed, of which 39 completed questionnaires were retrieved. Because of the low return, the quantitative findings were treated as descriptive rather than statistically generalizable to all farmers in New Lucena. Within the broader mixed-methods design, the survey served as one source of evidence for identifying indicative patterns in readiness, constraints, and support needs related to natural farming in the municipality.

Focus Group Discussions. Focus group discussions were conducted as part of the qualitative component to obtain in-depth accounts of farmers' experiences and perspectives regarding natural farming. One discussion involved 10 natural farmers, while another involved four conventional farming practitioners. The discussions were used to capture farmer perspectives beyond the household survey, including knowledge of natural farming, perceived barriers to adoption, labor demands, and satisfaction with existing extension support. Semi-structured guides were used to facilitate the discussions, and the local dialect was used to support participant comfort and richness of response. In the reporting of results, focus group participants were treated as anonymized farmer participants in order to protect confidentiality.

Participatory Workshops. Participatory workshops were conducted to deepen the qualitative component of the study and to generate collective insights on the transition to natural farming in New Lucena. These workshops involved selected leaders from OFPANELU and allied groups. The workshop activities included visioning, problem tree analysis, gap analysis, and SWOT analysis. Visioning was used to articulate a shared aspiration for New Lucena as a natural farming municipality. Problem tree analysis was used to identify root causes and effects of persistent barriers to natural farming. Gap analysis was used to examine differences between current conditions and the desired state of adoption. SWOT analysis was used to identify internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats affecting natural farming efforts in the municipality. Together, these workshop activities generated qualitative insights into farmers' aspirations, structural constraints, and institutional conditions relevant to natural farming transition.

Key Informant Interviews. Key informant interviews were conducted to deepen the study's understanding of the institutional, organizational, and policy conditions affecting natural farming in the municipality. Seven key informant interviews formed part of the qualitative component of the study. Informants represented relevant local and community-based perspectives, including those involved in agriculture, municipal planning, gender and development, farmer organization work, youth engagement, and development practice. These interviews were included to provide insight into gender participation, inter-agency collaboration, and policy-related constraints

affecting sustainable farming in New Lucena. To protect confidentiality, informants were reported using generalized participant categories rather than specific titles or names.

Policy and Document Review. A targeted policy and document review was also conducted to examine the local policy and institutional environment relevant to natural farming. This review focused on municipal ordinances, gender and development plans or frameworks, and other agriculture-related local policies and plans. Seven local ordinances, programs, and GAD-related frameworks were examined using a standardized checklist, and local government personnel were interviewed to validate the review findings. Within the broader mixed-methods design, this component contributed evidence on the presence of local support mechanisms and on gaps in implementation, coordination, and institutional follow-through. Because the review formed part of a situational analysis rather than a formal policy evaluation, claims about implementation were interpreted cautiously.

Data Analysis

Data analysis combined quantitative and qualitative procedures consistent with the study design. Quantitative survey data were organized using Microsoft Excel and analyzed through descriptive statistics, particularly frequency counts and cross-tabulations. These were used to identify patterns in knowledge, attitudes, skills, practices, gender roles, and training needs related to natural farming. Qualitative data from focus group discussions, key informant interviews, and participatory workshops were analyzed thematically. Transcripts and workshop notes were coded to identify recurring patterns, contradictions, and insights related to farmers' aspirations, barriers to adoption, and the local institutional environment. Triangulation across the different data sources was used to strengthen contextual interpretation, and summaries were cross-checked manually to support accuracy and rigor in the interpretation of results.

Ethical Considerations

The data used in this study were originally gathered as part of a situational analysis intended to support extension planning for natural farming in New Lucena, Iloilo, Philippines, rather than as a protocol submitted for formal ethics review. Under the institutional practice of the authors' university at the time of data collection, ethics review was not yet required for extension-research activities of this nature. Consequently, no ethics review board approval number applies to this study. Nevertheless, the study observed fundamental ethical principles for social research throughout data collection, analysis, and reporting. Participation in the household survey, focus group discussions, key informant interviews, and participatory workshops was voluntary. Participants were informed of the purpose of the study prior to participation, and informed consent was secured before data were collected. Although the municipality was identified as the unit of analysis because of the contextual and policy relevance of the study, no individual participant was identified by name in the manuscript. Quotations and qualitative accounts were reported using generalized participant labels, and potentially identifying combinations of details were removed or generalized to protect confidentiality, particularly in a small-community setting. Generative artificial intelligence was used only as a writing aid for language refinement and organization during manuscript preparation. All substantive aspects of the study, including study design, data collection, analysis, interpretation of findings, and final approval of the manuscript, remained the responsibility of the authors.

Methodological Limitations

Several methodological limitations should be noted. Although 200 household surveys were distributed, only 39 were retrieved; thus, the survey findings should be interpreted as descriptive of participating respondents rather than statistically representative of all farmers in New Lucena. Participation in the focus group discussions was also uneven, particularly among conventional farmers, whose group included only four participants because of limited availability. In addition, the policy review was limited to seven local policies and plans assessed for their relevance to sustainable and natural farming. These constraints were partly addressed through triangulation across the survey, focus group discussions, key informant interviews, participatory workshops, and document review. Table 1 summarizes the study's data sources and analytical purpose, while Figure 1 presents the overall workflow of the participatory mixed-methods situational ana

Table 1. Summary of Data Sources and Analytical Purpose

Data source	Participants / coverage	Main focus	Type of analysis
Household survey	39 retrieved questionnaires out of 200 distributed	Demographics, farm profiles, knowledge, attitudes, skills, practices, household roles, barriers, and support needs	Descriptive statistics and cross-tabulations
Focus group discussions	10 natural farmers; 4 conventional farmers	Farmer experiences, barriers to adoption, labor demands, and satisfaction with extension support	Thematic analysis
Participatory workshops	Selected OFPANELU leaders and allied groups	Visioning, problem tree analysis, gap analysis, and SWOT analysis	Thematic synthesis
Key informant interviews	7 local and community-based informants	Institutional, organizational, gender, youth, and policy-related conditions	Thematic analysis
Policy and document review	7 ordinances, programs, and GAD-related frameworks	Policy support, inclusiveness, implementation, coordination, and institutional follow-through	Checklist-based review and interpretive analysis

Figure 1. Participatory Mixed-Methods Situational Analysis Framework

Results

This section presents the results on the readiness of New Lucena, Iloilo, Philippines for transition to natural farming. Drawing on household surveys, focus group discussions, key informant interviews, participatory workshops, and policy and document review, the results describe the aspirations of participating respondents and stakeholders, the current knowledge, attitudes, skills, and practices related to natural farming, the gender and youth dimensions of participation, the major gaps between current and desired conditions, the enabling and hindering factors affecting adoption, and the organizational, institutional, and policy context shaping local readiness. Because only 39 of the 200 distributed questionnaires were retrieved, the quantitative findings are presented as descriptive of participating respondents rather than statistically generalizable to the wider farming population of New Lucena.

Aspirations and Perceived Value of Natural Farming

Among participating respondents and stakeholders, natural farming was associated with healthier food production, lower farming costs, environmental care, and broader community development in New Lucena. These aspirations extended beyond individual farm practice to a wider goal of establishing the municipality as a local model for natural farming. Survey and qualitative findings further showed that respondents valued natural farming not only for perceived health

and economic benefits, but also for community learning, visible demonstration, and broader local participation.

Table 2. Aspirations of Respondents and Stakeholders Toward Natural Farming in New Lucena, Iloilo (n = 39)

Aspiration / theme	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation
Natural farming is healthier than chemical-intensive farming	36	92.3%	Health and food safety were central to respondents' understanding of natural farming.
Natural farming reduces production costs	32	82.1%	Respondents associated natural farming with lower dependence on purchased farm inputs.
Demonstration farms in every barangay are needed	30	76.9%	Visible and practical examples were considered important for wider learning and acceptance.
Natural farming can increase profit	27	69.2%	Many respondents believed natural farming could improve farm income through lower costs and local inputs.
Respondents shared natural farming practices with neighbors	19	48.7%	Peer-to-peer learning was an important part of community-based aspiration and knowledge sharing.
Youth are involved in farm tasks	11	28.2%	Some intergenerational involvement exists, but youth participation remains limited.
Sustained youth interest in farming	6	15.4%	Long-term youth engagement was weak despite aspirations for continuity.

Table 2 shows that health and food safety were the strongest perceived benefits of natural farming, with 92.3% of respondents associating natural farming with healthier production. Economic considerations also figured prominently, as 82.1% associated natural farming with reduced production costs and 69.2% linked it with increased profit. At the same time, 76.9% expressed the need for demonstration farms in every barangay, indicating that respondents saw practical and visible examples as important for wider learning and local acceptance. Peer-to-peer knowledge sharing was also evident, with 48.7% reporting that they had already shared natural farming practices with neighbors. However, youth involvement remained limited: only 28.2% reported youth participation in farm tasks and only 15.4% reported sustained youth interest in farming. These findings suggest that while respondents held strong aspirations for natural farming as a healthier and more economically viable approach, continuity and broader social participation remained uneven.

Knowledge, Attitudes, Skills, and Practices

Survey and qualitative findings indicated that awareness of natural farming among participating respondents was relatively high, but practical knowledge, technical confidence, and sustained application remained more limited. Respondents generally expressed favorable attitudes toward natural farming, especially in relation to household health and reduced expenses, yet these positive perceptions did not always translate into consistent practice.

Table 3. Knowledge, Attitudes, Skills, and Practices of Respondents on Natural Farming (n = 39)

Dimension	Indicator	Frequency	Percentage
Knowledge	Know what natural farming is	36	92.3%
Knowledge	Can describe preparation of key natural farming inputs	11	28.2%
Attitudes	Associate natural farming with improved household health	33	84.6%
Attitudes	View natural farming as reducing production expenses	32	82.1%
Skills	Can confidently prepare natural farming inputs	14	35.9%
Practices	Use compost in some way	25	64.1%
Practices	Use fermented plant juice	17	43.6%
Practices	Practice crop rotation or diversification	12	30.8%
Practices	Continue using synthetic pesticides and fertilizers when needed	7	17.9%

As shown in Table 3, 92.3% of respondents reported that they knew what natural farming was, but only 28.2% said they could describe how to prepare key inputs such as fermented plant juice, fish amino acid, or bokashi compost. This gap suggests that general awareness was not matched by equally strong technical understanding. In terms of attitudes, 84.6% associated natural farming with improved household health and 82.1% associated it with reduced production expenses, indicating broad positive perceptions among participating respondents. However, only 35.9% reported that they could confidently prepare natural farming inputs, which points to a more limited level of practical confidence. In terms of practices, 64.1% reported using compost in some way, 43.6% reported using fermented plant juice, and 30.8% reported practicing crop rotation or diversification. At the same time, 17.9% reported continued use of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers when needed. Taken together, these findings indicate selective rather than comprehensive adoption of natural farming practices, with more favorable perceptions than technical confidence or sustained practice.

Gender and Youth Participation

Gender and youth dimensions further shaped the local picture of readiness. The data indicated that women comprised a substantial portion of the respondent group and were actively involved in household-level natural farming practices such as composting, backyard gardening, and the preparation of organic inputs. Specifically, 61.5% of the survey sample, or 24 of 39 respondents, were women. This suggests that household-level natural farming already had a practical place within everyday labor and domestic production systems. In contrast, youth participation remained limited and inconsistent. Only 28.2% of respondents reported youth involvement in farm tasks, while only 15.4% reported sustained youth interest in farming. These patterns suggest that some aspects of natural farming were already embedded in household and community practice, but intergenerational continuity remained weak among participating respondents.

Table 4. Gender and Youth Dimensions of Participation in Natural Farming (n = 39)

Dimension	Indicator	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation
Gender	Women in the survey sample	24	61.5%	Women comprised a substantial share of respondents and were visible in household-level natural farming activities.
Youth	Youth involved in farm tasks	11	28.2%	Some intergenerational participation was present, but involvement remained limited.
	Sustained youth interest in farming	6	15.4%	Long-term youth engagement was weak.

Note: Qualitative findings further indicated that women were actively involved in composting, backyard gardening, and the preparation of organic inputs, although separate task-specific frequencies were not reported in the survey.

The findings indicate that women comprised a substantial portion of the respondent group and were visibly involved in household-level natural farming activities. At the same time, youth participation remained limited: only 28.2% of respondents reported youth involvement in farm tasks, while only 15.4% reported sustained youth interest in farming. These patterns suggest that some aspects of natural farming were already embedded in household and community practice, but intergenerational continuity remained weak among participating respondents.

Gaps Between Current and Desired Conditions

Findings from the participatory workshops and related qualitative data indicated a clear gap between current farming conditions and the desired state of natural farming adoption in New Lucena. Respondents and stakeholders described a desired future in which natural farming would be supported by visible demonstration farms, reliable access to materials, sustained technical assistance, market support, and stronger institutional coordination. In contrast, current conditions were described as uneven, with limited follow-up extension assistance, irregular access to supplies and materials, weak market and certification mechanisms, and fragmented coordination among actors. These findings suggest that the transition to natural farming was constrained not only by farm-level technical issues, but also by broader support-system gaps that affected continuity and scale.

Enabling and Hindering Factors

The findings showed that natural farming adoption in New Lucena was shaped by both enabling and hindering conditions. Local ordinances, training opportunities, farmer networks, and household-level participation provided support for natural farming, while irregular program delivery, weak monitoring, limited market support, low youth participation, and poor coordination constrained broader uptake.

Table 5. Enabling and Hindering Factors Affecting Natural Farming Adoption in New Lucena, Iloilo

Category	Factor	Evidence from findings	Implication
Enabling	Local policy support and institutional willingness	Local ordinances and programs such as the organic trading post, no-burning rule, Bantay <i>Kaumahan</i> (farm field) Task Force, and <i>Sagana Ani</i> (abundant harvest) program were identified as formal supports. Respondents also mentioned LGU and project-based training and free inputs, although these were intermittent.	Natural farming had some formal and institutional backing at the local level.
Enabling	Existing farmer networks and experienced practitioners	OFPANELU and farmer-to-farmer learning supported local adoption; 48.7% (19 of 39 respondents) had shared their knowledge of natural farming with neighbors.	Peer learning and organized farmer networks served as practical support mechanisms.
Enabling	Gender inclusion in household-level practices	61.5% (24 respondents) of the sample were women, many of whom were involved in composting, backyard gardening, and preparation of organic inputs.	Women played an important role in sustaining household-level natural farming practices.
Hindering	Irregular program implementation and support	60.5% (23 respondents) identified inconsistent supplies such as drums, molasses, and seeds as a major obstacle. Training was described as infrequent and lacking follow-up support.	Weak continuity in support limited sustained practice after training.
Hindering	Weak monitoring, evaluation, and accountability	Respondents and local personnel described programs as having limited follow-up and weak ongoing oversight.	Lack of monitoring reduced program effectiveness and continuity.
Hindering	Limited market access and certification mechanisms	Respondents noted difficulty selling products at higher prices because they lacked recognized labels or proof of organic or natural farming status.	Weak market systems reduced incentives for broader adoption.
Hindering	Declining youth engagement	Only 15.4% (6 respondents) reported sustained youth participation in agriculture.	Low youth involvement threatened long-term continuity of adoption.
Hindering	Coordination gaps across stakeholders	LGUs, NGOs, and state universities were described as often working separately, with limited formal planning and coordination.	Fragmented coordination weakened collective support for natural farming.

Table 5 indicates that enabling conditions were already present, but they coexisted with persistent structural constraints. Local policy support, peer learning, and women’s participation

in household-level activities provided a foundation for natural farming. However, the broader transition remained constrained by inconsistent program support, weak monitoring, limited market incentives, declining youth engagement, and fragmented coordination. These findings suggest that wider adoption depended not only on farmer interest, but also on stronger institutional continuity and collective support mechanisms.

Organizational, Partnership, and Policy Support

The findings further indicated that natural farming in New Lucena was supported by multiple organizational and institutional actors, although these supports were unevenly coordinated. OFPANELU emerged as an important community-based platform for farmer-to-farmer learning, mutual support, and collective participation. Non-government actors were also reported to complement local efforts, especially when immediate material or training support was needed. At the national level, the Department of Agriculture, through regional and provincial offices under the National Organic Agriculture Program, was identified as a source of support such as sprayers, vermicast, and compost barrels. However, respondents described this support as irregular and insufficient relative to local demand. Survey findings also showed that 60.5% of respondents, or 23 of 39, reported not having seen any recent government briefings on natural farming. Across these actors, the data pointed to a recurring coordination gap. While several groups were active in the municipality, only a few respondents could identify an active venue for regular coordination, and collaborations were described as depending largely on personal networks or project-based arrangements rather than formalized mechanisms. Overall, policy and partnership support was present across multiple sectors, but its effectiveness was constrained by weak continuity, limited institutionalization, and uneven coordination.

Figure 2 summarizes selected indicators from the survey findings, highlighting the contrast between high awareness and favorable perceptions of natural farming, on one hand, and lower technical confidence and weak youth continuity, on the other.

Figure 2. Selected Readiness Indicators for Natural Farming Adoption in New Lucena, Iloilo (n = 39)

This figure would highlight the study’s clearest pattern: high awareness and positive attitudes alongside lower technical confidence and weak youth continuity.

Discussion

The findings suggest that readiness for transition to natural farming in New Lucena is present but incomplete. Among participating respondents and stakeholders, natural farming was associated with improved household health, reduced dependence on purchased inputs, and broader community value through demonstration, peer learning, and local participation. At the same time, the transition remained constrained by limited technical confidence, inadequate access to inputs, weak follow-up support, and uneven coordination across institutions. Taken together, these findings indicate that readiness for natural farming in the municipality cannot be understood simply as a matter of favorable farmer attitudes. Rather, it reflects the interaction of farmer motivation, local organizational support, and the institutional conditions needed to sustain adoption over time.

One of the clearest patterns in the study is the gap between positive perception and sustained technical practice. While most participating respondents reported knowing what natural farming is and associated it with health and cost benefits, much smaller proportions reported being able to describe the preparation of key inputs or prepare such inputs confidently. This suggests that awareness alone did not automatically translate into technical capability or routine farm-level application. Recent studies from Asia have similarly shown that adoption of sustainable agricultural practices depends not only on farmers' attitudes, but also on human, social, financial, and physical capital, as well as access to technical advisory support [8,9]. These broader findings are consistent with the pattern observed in New Lucena, where interest in natural farming was high but technical confidence and sustained practice remained uneven.

The findings also underscore the importance of extension continuity and material support in shaping adoption. In New Lucena, respondents and stakeholders repeatedly pointed to inadequate access to supplies, weak follow-up after training, and irregular program delivery as barriers to sustained practice. This aligns with current Philippine policy directions, which emphasize that organic and sustainable agriculture require integrated research, development, and extension support rather than one-time project interventions [3,4]. These policy directions support the interpretation that wider adoption in New Lucena depends not only on farmer willingness, but also on more consistent institutional follow-through and local support mechanisms.

Gender and youth findings in the study further suggest that local readiness is socially differentiated. Women were substantially represented in the respondent group and were actively involved in composting, backyard gardening, and the preparation of organic inputs, indicating that household-level natural farming practices were already embedded in gendered labor arrangements. However, youth participation remained limited and sustained youth interest in farming was weak. This pattern is important because long-term transition depends not only on current practice, but also on intergenerational continuity. Recent Philippine initiatives such as the Youth Internship Program on Organic Agriculture and the Youth Scholarship Grant on Organic Farming indicate that national and regional institutions now recognize youth engagement as a strategic issue in sustaining organic and sustainable agriculture [5,7]. The New Lucena findings therefore reinforce the relevance of such interventions and suggest that local extension efforts may need to include more deliberate youth-oriented strategies if natural farming is to be sustained over time.

Another important result is that policy presence did not necessarily translate into effective implementation. The study found that local ordinances, programs, and organizational actors were already present, yet respondents still described weak monitoring, inconsistent support, and fragmented coordination among government, farmer groups, and partner institutions. This reflects a common challenge in agricultural transition: formal policy support may exist, but implementation quality and institutional coordination determine whether such support becomes meaningful in practice. Current Philippine planning for agriculture, research, and local development also emphasizes coordination, resilience, and locally responsive implementation [1,3]. In this respect, the findings from New Lucena suggest that local readiness for natural farming is partly a governance issue. Policies and programs may create enabling conditions, but their effectiveness depends on continuity, accountability, inter-agency cooperation, and regular mechanisms for collective planning.

The study's broader contribution lies in showing that situational analysis for SUC extension can function as more than a needs-assessment or profiling activity. In this case, the combined use of survey findings, qualitative farmer accounts, participatory workshop outputs, and policy review made it possible to assess readiness for natural farming not only at the level of farmer attitudes and practices, but also in relation to technical support, organizational capacity, institutional coordination, and inclusiveness. This positions the study as an extension-oriented innovation in method application: it demonstrates how participatory mixed-methods situational analysis can be used as a strategic planning tool for developing gender-responsive and community-based extension frameworks, especially in localities where transition depends on both social readiness and institutional support. In this sense, the study is also relevant to local efforts to advance the Sustainable Development Goals through agricultural transition, particularly in relation to sustainable food systems, inclusive participation, and stronger institutional partnerships. Recent Philippine and regional policy directions that emphasize localized extension, capacity building, and inclusive agricultural transformation further support the relevance of this type of integrated evidence-building approach [3-7].

At the same time, the findings should be interpreted within the limits of the study design. The survey component was based on only 39 retrieved questionnaires, the conventional farmer focus group had limited participation, and the policy review covered only seven local policies and plans. For this reason, the study does not claim statistical generalizability to all farmers in New Lucena. Its value lies instead in providing a triangulated, municipality-specific evidence base for understanding readiness conditions and designing locally grounded extension responses. In this sense, the study contributes both empirical insight into natural farming transition in New Lucena and a practical model for extension-oriented situational analysis that may be useful to other SUCs and local governments working in comparable rural contexts.

Conclusion

This study assessed the readiness of New Lucena, Iloilo, Philippines for transition to natural farming using a participatory mixed-methods situational analysis. The findings indicate that full readiness has not yet been achieved, but that the municipality already exhibits emerging social,

organizational, and policy conditions that may support such transition. Among participating respondents and stakeholders, natural farming was associated with improved household health, lower dependence on purchased inputs, community learning, and local agricultural improvement. At the same time, wider adoption remained constrained by limited technical confidence, inadequate access to inputs, weak follow-up extension support, low youth participation, and uneven coordination among supporting institutions.

The study therefore suggests that readiness for natural farming in New Lucena is present but incomplete, and that future progress will depend not only on farmer interest, but also on stronger technical, organizational, and institutional support systems. The results further show that women already play important roles in household-level natural farming practices, while sustained youth engagement remains limited, indicating the need for more inclusive and intergenerational extension strategies. Existing local policies and programs provide some formal support for sustainable and natural farming, but their practical value is reduced by weak implementation, limited continuity, and fragmented coordination.

Beyond its municipality-specific findings, the study also demonstrates how participatory mixed-methods situational analysis can be used as an extension-oriented planning tool for state universities and colleges. By integrating survey findings, farmer narratives, participatory workshop outputs, key informant perspectives, and policy review, the study moves situational analysis beyond descriptive baseline generation and toward actionable, gender-responsive, and community-based extension planning. In this sense, the paper contributes not only a local evidence base for New Lucena, but also a practical model for SUC extension work in comparable agricultural transition contexts. The study's practical implications are likewise relevant to the Sustainable Development Goals by linking natural farming transition with sustainable food systems, gender-responsive participation, youth engagement, and stronger local institutional collaboration.

These findings suggest the need for sustained farmer training with follow-up support, improved access to natural farming inputs, demonstration-based learning at the barangay level, stronger inter-agency coordination, and more deliberate strategies for youth engagement and gender-responsive programming. Future studies may build on this work through larger samples, comparative municipal analysis, and technical assessments of productivity, soil quality, and environmental outcomes. Given the limited survey return and the municipality-specific scope of the inquiry, the findings should be interpreted as descriptive of participating respondents and stakeholders rather than statistically representative of the entire farming population of New Lucena.

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